

Micro-credentials in higher education: a review and bibliometric

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to conduct a comprehensive review of research on “Micro-credentials in higher education” by doing a bibliometric analysis of 85 journal articles published between 2015 and 2023, obtained from the Scopus database. This study focuses on quantifying the number of publications and citations, as well as examining subject areas, connections, universities, countries, and identifying the most productive and prominent researchers. Apart from that, this research also identifies research topics that researchers have been working on in recent years. The findings show that publications and citations have increased in the last three years. The United States, Australia, and Canada are the most productive countries on this topic. T. J. Newby is the most productive researcher, while the most influential writer is D. -K. Mah. TechTrends and The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology are the journals that publish the most research. The university that made the top contribution was Purdue University (United States). The results of data analysis show that collaboration between authors researching “Micro-credentials in higher education” still needs improvement. This research contributes as a basis for further research in enriching and developing knowledge about micro-credentials, especially in higher education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The very rapid development of technology poses challenges to the flexibility of the existing education system. The education system owned by educational institutions needs to be improved to make it possible to offer micro-credentials via online platforms. Micro-credentials are the latest educational trend as developments in digital technology change the way learning and teaching become more effective [1]–[3]. Micro-credentials are built on discourse about the changing role of higher education in the 21st century. To address labor market demands, new skills are offered, and services are expanded for evaluating and recognizing prior learning experiences [4]. Moreover, today, entrepreneurs are eager to invest in human resources [5], [6].

Based on this perspective, micro-credentials are not intended to replace traditional higher education methods. Instead, they aim to introduce innovative approaches to professional development, recognition, and assessment of prior learning [7], [5]. Educational institutions are now given a new role as organizers of micro-credentials in the education ecosystem [8], [9]. It is essential to be more accurate in micro-credentials and realize that it is not only oriented toward the output produced. But it must also investigate the challenges and risks that can arise. Therefore, micro-credentials advance by entering a persuasion phase, during which stakeholders reassess the benefits and challenges of implementing this approach [5], [10].

Along with this growth, quite a number of researchers are interested in conducting studies on micro-credentials. Micro-credentials are increasingly popular among academics and practitioners in the education sector [11], [12]. Several previous studies related to micro-credentials have been identified. Previous research analyzed bibliometric approaches with the theme of implementing micro-credentials in higher education [13]. The research findings suggest that micro-credentials in higher education are attracting considerable interest from the academic community. Although researchers have examined different aspects of the topic using various methods and theories, more research is needed to grasp how technology affects different stakeholder's perspectives entirely. Furthermore, this study emphasizes the need to address critical areas of research that are necessary for the advancement of the existing body of knowledge on the implementation of micro-credentials in higher education.

Other research that examines Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) using a bibliometric approach to identify research trends, journals, regions and institutions with a high H index, scientific collaborations, research topics, distribution of issues in countries/regions, productive institutions, and distribution of subjects used in MOOCs [14]. Between 2008 and 2019, 1,788 publications were sourced from three significant databases: Web of Science (WOS), Scopus, and Education Resources Information Center (ERIC). This bibliometric analysis offers researchers a detailed and comprehensive overview of current MOOC research, pinpointing emerging research topics and identifying potential collaborative partners for future MOOC-related investigations.

In addition, another study investigated online learning in higher education around the world during COVID-19 using bibliometric analysis [15]. The researchers employed co-citation analysis and text mining facilitated by VOS viewer to collect and analyze research patterns and subjects discussed in peer-reviewed documents published from January 2020 to August 2021. The study reveals that researchers from 103 countries or territories across the globe conducted investigations on a range of subjects, including the utilization of diverse technologies and learning approaches, curriculum restructuring, student perspectives, and the psychological consequences of online learning resulting from the pandemic. This study also examines online higher education's present and upcoming difficulties, prioritizing the implementation of creative teaching methods in online learning. Additionally, it acknowledges the increasing but uneven availability of literature related to these research findings.

Bibliometric analysis is a quantitative method for studying and analyzing a scientific publication. This method uses various statistical indicators to map research trends, identify collaborations between researchers, and assess the impact of research. Regarding bibliometric analysis of micro-credential studies, as far as we know, there has yet to be any research on micro-credentials that analyzes science and mapping performance in recent years. So, this research investigates studies on micro-credentials in the 2015-2023 period using the Scopus database. Then, previous bibliometric research only focused on implementing micro-credentials in higher education. This is a gap in this research, so researchers aim to analyze research trends regarding Micro-credentials through bibliometric analysis. This analysis encompasses both performance analysis and science mapping. This research contributes to the field by providing an overview of the growth of MOOC research over the past five years and serves as a comprehensive reference for other researchers studying micro-credentials in higher education.

2. METHOD

The bibliographic method was employed in this study. The bibliometric approach applies quantitative approaches to analyze scientific literature [16], [17]. The data source for this work is the Scopus database. Scopus, one of the top scientific databases, enjoys great credibility for offering thorough and high-quality scientific data [18], [19]. This research analysis has two main components: i) the use of bibliometric mapping to study trends in micro-credentials in higher education, and ii) the analysis of indexed keywords in publications to identify research clusters and gain insights into research themes associated with micro-credentials in higher education. The research uses VOS viewer software to facilitate data interpretation trenchwork, overlay density visual visualizations. These visualizations readability and comprehension. Software like VOS viewer can offer insights into network metrics and clustering, which are valuable for bibliometric study studies [20], [21]. There are 5 bibliometric analysis steps used in this research, as presented in Figure 1 [22]–[24].

2.1. Defining search keywords

In bibliometric studies, selecting search keywords is very important because these keywords are the basis for identifying, extracting, and analyzing relevant literature. The keyword search selected to be used in the literature search in the Scopus Database carried out on September 4, 2023, was “micro-credentials” OR “micro-credential” OR “digital badges” OR “virtual badges” AND “higher education”. As an initial step, the

researcher selected document features in the Scopus database; then, these keywords were written in the subsection of the document feature, namely “document search,” with a choice of search formats “article title,” “abstract,” and “keyword”.

Figure 1. Bibliometric steps analysis

2.2. Initial search results

The search yielded 184 documents suitable for “micro-credentials in higher education” sourced from Articles, conference paper, book chapter, conference review, review, book, editorials, erratum, and all languages. These documents were also output without using a time range setting. This comprehensive data set provides a strong foundation for conducting bibliometric analysis.

2.3. Refining the search results

Several specific criteria were established to obtain documents suitable for this research. First, the document title contains the keywords “micro-credentials” OR “micro-credential” OR “digital badges” OR “virtual badges” AND “higher education”. Second, the document is written in English. Third, the documents are derived from reputable journal and article sources. Moreover, the records that were released between the years 2015 and 2023. The process of systematically selecting documents that meet the inclusion criteria is accomplished through four sequential steps: i) identification, ii) screening, iii) eligibility, and iv) inclusion [16], [25]. Figure 2 presents details of these four steps. Based on Figure 2, there were 85 articles related to micro-credentials in higher education sourced from journal article document types, in English, published in the 2015-2023 period.

Figure 2. Steps in refining the search result of bibliometric analysis related to “micro-credentials in higher education”

2.4. Compiling the initial data statistics

Documents that satisfy the criteria are then employed as a research data source. The data was acquired from the Scopus database in two formats: comma separated values (CSV) and research information system (RIS). Both types provide crucial article details, such as bibliometric and bibliographic metadata [26]–[28].

2.5. Analyzing the data

The data analysis in this research involves conducting performance analysis and science mapping. The bibliometric meta-data was analyzed using VOS Viewer software to examine co-authorship data, bibliographic merging, keyword occurrences, and citations. Bibliographic coupling involves determining the relationships between items such as publications, journals, and authors by considering the number of shared resources. Examining the frequency of keywords provides insights into the patterns and developments within a particular area of research as time progresses [29]. Therefore, the bibliometric approach is efficient for

identifying trends in certain research fields. Citation analysis helps researchers detect popular research topics that other researchers are working on [30]. The results of the analysis are then presented in the form of a table or network visualization map.

Figure 3 shows that the development of publications, both the number of publications and citations related to micro-credentials in higher education is relatively constant from the period 2015 to 2017, and starting in early 2018 until 2023 the number of citations relatively increases, while the number of publications remains relatively constant up to in 2020. Furthermore, we can observe an increase in the number of publications from 2021 to 2023. Furthermore, the average number of publications per year is 9.4, while the average number of citations per year is 91.4. This data informs us that there is a positive correlation between the number of publications and citations related to micro-credentials in higher education, meaning that the greater the number of publications, the more citations [31].

Figure 3. The development of publication and citation of research about micro-credentials in higher education

Figure 4 shows the distribution of publications by countries, publications on “micro-credentials in higher education” cover 26 countries. Researchers obtained data on the 10 countries with the top number of documents, namely the United States, in first place with 34 publications. The second place is occupied by Australia with a total of 14 publications, third is Canada with a total of 9 publications, fourth is the United Kingdom with a total of 5 publications, Germany and Spain with a total of 5 publications for each country. Meanwhile, China, Finland, and New Zealand each produced 2 publications.

Figure 4. Publication on micro-credentials in higher education research according to countries

Figure 5 shows the research area subjects interested in micro-credentials in higher education. Among these subject areas, “social science” is the top subject area producing 54.2% of publications between 2015 and 2023. Furthermore, the subject area “computer science” is in second place producing 23.9%, in third place is

the subject area “business, management” produced 5.6%, in fourth place the subject area “medicine” produced 2.8%, while the subject area “mathematics” which was in fifth place produced 2.1%.

Figure 5. Publication micro-credentials in higher education according to research areas

We can observe the universities that made the top contribution in Figure 6. Among these universities, Purdue University (United States) is the top university that has contributed related to “micro-credentials in higher education” with a total of 6 publications. In second place, Dublin City University (Ireland) with 4 publications. The third to fifth directors with 3 publications each include the University of Toronto (Canada), Athabasca University (Canada), Universitat Potsdam (Germany). Meanwhile, in sequence, the University of South Africa (South Africa), Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (Spain), University of Limerick (Ireland), Tampere University (Finland) and Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapeli (Norwegian) with a total of 2 publications.

Figure 6. Publication micro-credentials in higher education according to universities

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Co-authorship analysis

Co-authorship analysis is a science mapping technique that assumes publications that are frequently cited together have similar themes [32], [33]. This technique is basically used to present social interactions between authors related to a particular research topic [34]. The results of the analysis can be used to measure the quality of the structure in a particular research field [35], for example the underlying topic [36]. In co-authorship, two publications are connected when they appear together in the reference list of another publication, apart from that, through co-authorship analysis researchers can also find influential researchers in a particular field [16]. Co-authorship can also be interpreted as a form of research collaboration involving

several parties such as researchers, institutions, organizations and society [37]. Collaboration between researchers in each scientific discipline has different levels. The more often authors collaborate, the greater the collaboration in terms of research that can be achieved [38], [39]. Differences in the level of collaboration between scientific disciplines can be influenced by several factors, such as demographics, researcher information behavior, and gender [40], [41].

During the 2015-2023 period, 160 authors contributed to this research topic, either singly or in collaboration. Figure 7 shows a network visualization of co-authorship, marked with circles representing researchers, and the network represents relationships between researchers. The data results show that 160 authors have written at least 1 article, divided into 82 clusters with different colors. The results of the co-authorship analysis are centered on Jr. Don Olcott, who is a professor at the University of South Africa, Oldenburg University, and is active in conducting research in the field of micro-credentials. The network shows that there is a relationship, including with McGreal. The connection between the links shows that the authors conducted research together, and the stronger the relationship between the authors, the larger the circle formed. The visualization graph shows that most of the authors are not connected because they do not collaborate with each other. A collection of circles without a network appears to dominate so that we can interpret that research collaboration on the topic of micro-credentials in higher education is still very small. This is certainly a challenge and opportunity for researchers to build collaboration. Collaborative research can empirically improve research quality [42], articles tend to be cited more when they have more authors [42]–[45]. Apart from that, collaborative research can also improve the quality of an organization's research, the more collaborative research there is, the quantity and quality of the institution's research will also increase [42].

Figure 7. Co-authorship network map in micro-credentials in higher education

3.2. Most influential researchers

The number of publications is used to indicate influential documents, while the number of citations is used to indicate influential authors and sources. First, influential documents are represented by the top 10 documents with the highest citations obtained from the Scopus database, as we can see in Table 1. Table 2 shows that the most influential document related to the micro-credentials in higher education study was written by D. -K. Mah in 2016 with the title *Learning Analytics and Digital Badges: Potential Impact on Student Retention in Higher Education* [46]. This document has been cited by other relevant research 81 times. An example is Alamri *et al.* [47] with the title *Learning Technology Models that Support Personalization within Blended Learning Environments in Higher Education*. Furthermore, productive authors are represented by the top 5 authors with the highest publications while influential authors are represented by the top 5 authors with the highest citations.

Table 1. Most influential researchers in micro-credentials in higher education ranked by cites

No	Year	Authors	Title	Source	Cites	Publisher
1	2016	Mah [46]	Learning analytics and digital badges: potential impact on student retention in higher education	Technology, Knowledge and Learning	81	Springer
2	2021	Alamri <i>et al.</i> [47]	Learning technology models that support personalization within blended learning environments in higher education	TechTrends	47	Springer
3	2018	Carey and Stefaniak [48]	An exploration of the utility of digital badging in higher education settings	Educational Technology Research and Development	47	Springer
4	2017	Dyjur and Lindstrom [49]	Perceptions and uses of digital badges for professional learning development in higher education	TechTrends	42	Springer
5	2020	Facey-Shaw <i>et al.</i> [50]	Do badges affect intrinsic motivation in introductory programming students?	Simulation and Gaming	34	SAGE Publications Inc.
6	2018	Cheng <i>et al.</i> [51]	Goal setting and open digital badges in higher education	TechTrends	33	Springer
7	2021	Selvaratnam and Sankey [52]	An integrative literature review of the implementation of micro-credentials in higher education: implications for practice in Australasia	Journal of Teaching and Learning for Graduate	25	Deakin University
8	2020	Newby and Cheng [53]	Instructional digital badges: effective learning tools	Employability Educational Technology Research and Development	24	Springer
9	2021	Brown <i>et al.</i> [54]	The global micro-credential landscape: charting a new credential ecology for lifelong learning	Journal of Learning for Development	24	Commonwealth of Learning
10	2022	Wheelahlan and Moodie [55]	Gig qualifications for the gig economy: micro-credentials and the "hungry mile"	Higher Education	24	Springer

Table 2. Most productive and influential researchers in micro-credentials in higher education

The productive authors			The influential authors		
Author	Institution/country	Total publication	Author	Total citation	Institution/country
T. J. Newby	Purdue University/USA	5	D. -K. Mah [46]	81	University of Potsdam/Germany
M. Brown	Dublin City University/Ireland	3	H.A. Alamri, S. Watson, and W. Watson [47]	47	King Saud University, Saudi Arabia
Z. Cheng	Purdue University/USA	3	K. L. Carey, and J. E. Stefaniak [48]	47	Old Dominion University, USA
D. -K. Mah	University of Potsdam/Germany	3	P. Dyjur, and G. Lindstrom [49]	42	University of Calgary, Canada
R. McGreal	Athabasca University/Canada	3	Facey-Shaw, L. Specht, P. M. van Rosmalen, and J. Bartley Bryan [50]	34	University of Technology Jamaica

Of the 160 authors involved in this research, T. J. Newby is the most productive author who has published 5 documents related to micro-credentials in higher education research affiliated with Purdue University (USA). One of the publications is entitled *Instructional Digital Badges: Effective Learning Tools* [53]. In the following positions, from second to fifth, there were the same number of publications, namely three. Brown *et al.* [54] occupies the second position; one of his publications is entitled *A Strategic Institutional Response to Micro-Credentials: Key Questions for Educational Leaders*. Cheng *et al.* [51] occupies the third position; one of his publications is entitled *Goal Setting and Open Digital Badges in Higher Education*. D. -K. Mah [46] occupies the fourth position. One of her publications is *Learning Analytics and Digital Badges: Potential Impact on Student Retention in Higher Education*. Next in fifth position is McGreal and Jr [2], with one of his publications entitled *A Strategic Reset: micro-credentials for Higher Education Leaders*. Meanwhile, the most influential writer regarding micro-credentials in Higher Education is D. -K. Mah [46] who is affiliated with the University of Potsdam (Germany). The document has been cited by other relevant studies approximately 81 times. Meanwhile, in second and third positions with the same number of citations are Alamri [47], who is affiliated with King Saud University (Saudi Arabia), and Watson [47] who is affiliated with Old Dominion University (USA), both of whom have been cited around 47 times.

career advancement and student engagement. This research can provide valuable insight into how micro-credential learning can be designed and implemented to achieve optimal student learning outcomes.

Next is the keyword governance. Visualization findings show that the keyword government has the potential for further development due to its low occurrence rate. The government has an important role related to micro-credentials [62], [12]. Researchers can explore several aspects of micro-credentials and the government. Studies could be conducted to evaluate the influence of government policy on the development, implementation, and recognition of micro-credentials, including an analysis of the impact of policies on accessibility, quality, and public acceptance of micro-credentials. Other research could explore the government's recognition of micro-credentials in formal and informal education systems. This includes the integration of micro-credentials into the curriculum, acceptance by educational institutions, and recognition in the selection or promotion process. Another topic that could potentially be explored is the role of government in identifying job market skills needs and guiding the development of relevant micro-credentials programs. This may include analysis of labor market needs, collaboration with industry, and development of appropriate skills programs. This research can provide insight into how the government can support developing and recognizing micro-credentials as an integral part of the national education and training system.

Alternative credentials are the next keyword that has great potential to be explored. Alternative credentials are a form of recognition of learning and achievements obtained outside traditional formal educational pathways, such as a bachelor's degree or diploma [63]. In the context of skills development and continuing education, alternative credentials and micro-credentials can complement each other to provide solutions that are more flexible and responsive to the needs of learners and the job market [64]. Research on alternative credentials can cover various aspects. Studies could explore the extent to which alternative credentials are accepted and recognized by stakeholders, including employers, educational institutions, and the general public. This includes an analysis of perceptions about the value of alternative credentials in meeting labor market needs. Through research in this area, we can better understand the role of alternative credentials in education and the job market and the factors that influence their development, recognition, and acceptance.

4. CONCLUSION

The following can be concluded regarding the literature micro-credentials in higher education between 2015 and 2023 published by Scopus based on keyword analysis: i) The average annual publication rate is 9.4 articles; ii) The United States, Australia, Canada, Ireland, and the United Kingdom produced more publications on micro-credentials. Although the United States is one of the countries that publish more papers, it is not the country with the most influential researchers. Still, Germany produces the most influential researchers with the highest number of citations in publications, with researchers named D. -K. Mah and iii) Co-occurrence analysis highlights the lack of research on "educational technology," "learning," "government," and "alternative credentials." Based on the results of this data analysis, the number of studies on this issue has been relatively small in recent years.

This research has the following limitations: i) Scopus was the sole data collection tool used by the researchers, ii) Publications with in-press status were included in the research data, and iii) The terms micro-credentials, micro-credentials, digital badges, and virtual badges were associated with higher education during the data search, despite the fact that micro-credentials are not exclusively associated with higher education. Nevertheless, the data collection process is comparable because Scopus has recently published micro-credential studies. In future research, it is possible to integrate many approaches to conduct a theoretical analysis of micro-credentials. For instance, one may combine bibliometrics with systematic literature review (SLR) or SLR with meta-analysis. This research contributes by conducting a thorough keyword analysis to provide an overview of the existing literature on micro-credentials, particularly in higher education institutions.

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